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How environmental perception affects players' in-game behaviors? Towards developing games in compliance with Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract:

Several research studies have pointed out that players' in-game behaviors might be affected by different individual differences, such as player type, personality, etc. However, limited information is found about whether players' environmental perceptions might impact their in-game behaviors towards the environment while playing. To address this research gap, this study analyzes the in-game behaviors data of 640 players within *Nintendo's Animal Crossing: New Horizons (ACNH)*, as well as their environmental perceptions based on the revised New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) scale, using open data sourced and adapted from Vuong et al. (2021) from the Science Data Bank repository. The obtained results revealed that players' environmental perceptions might impact their in-game behaviors, however this is not always true; the obtained results also revealed that players might behave within the game against their beliefs and perceptions just to level-up in the game. For instance, anti-anthropocentrism players, who are environment-caring, are found to harm the nature within the game. The findings of this study can help to understand how people with different environmental perceptions might behave, hence promoting ecological behaviors. Additionally, they can also help to reveal how to design games that can emphasize environment-friendly behaviors, hence helping to achieve the sustainable development goals of United Nations (UN).

Keywords: environmental perception; games; in-game behaviors; compliance design; Sustainable development goals

1. Introduction

Digital technologies are playing an increasing role in the global agenda towards environmentalism. Particularly, digital games are recognized as effective educational tools that can help in assessing and fostering environmentally friendly attitudes, behaviors, and practices that ensure the sustainability of the environment (Janakiraman et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2018). The rationale behind environmental sustainability is that human perceptions and behavior impact how they interact with the physical world, hence, the need to encourage attitudinal and behavioral intentions that ensure the safety and welfare of the environment both in the short and long term. Environmental sustainability is important presently and in the future because it can solve many of the complex problems facing our planet (Janakiraman et al., 2018). It is believed that serious environmental games can better provide an understanding of practical environmental sustainability challenges through awareness (Madani et al., 2017). The fun, attractive, and immersive nature of games makes them suitable for them to be employed in understanding and encouraging environmental sustainability.

For example, UNESCO (2018) developed an environmental sustainability development recycling bag game with the aim of helping participants to grasp the concept of sustainable development, resource management, and consumption on the environment and humans. A systematic review also showed that serious games and gamification have been used to engage consumers in pro-environmental behaviors (Morganti et al., 2017). Janakiraman et al. (2021) also demonstrated the effectiveness of digital games in promoting environmentally friendly attitudes and behaviors. In another study, a life-cycle assessment (LCA) game was developed to assess the environmental impact or performance (e.g., climate change, occupation land, toxicity, fossil depletion) of a manufacturing company (Perini et al., 2018). In environmental game-based learning, Svensson (2016) mentioned that it is essential to understand the perceptions of people that guide their decisions in gaming environments.

That is, the general perception and personality traits of game players are influential factors in their in-game behavior in the virtual world. For example, Worth and Book (2015) found a connection between personality and dimensions of behavior in online role-playing games. Casper et al. (2021) observed a relationship between political ideology, environmental values and beliefs, and in-game activities. An investigation into how a personality trait, “Machiavellianism” (low honesty and humility), predicts trustworthiness in a one-shot

experimental bargaining game revealed that players with higher Machiavellianism scores were more likely to defect while unprovoked (Gunnthorsdottir et al., 2002).

Moreover, Faiola et al. (2013) showed that perceptions of flow (an enjoyable state of consciousness) and telepresence (feeling of inclusion in an online environment) are interrelated and may have an influence on attitude and behavior during virtual game-based learning. Merrill et al. (2022) also surveyed people to know their COVID-19 perceptions and beliefs and engaged them in a serious game to examine their behavioral responses and observed that their general perceptions about susceptibility to COVID-19 shaped their behavioral decisions during game play. That is, an individual perception, beliefs, or personality traits have the ability to incite behavioral response in a game-playing situation.

1.1.Environmental perceptions and in-game behavior

Despite the growing interest in promoting environmental sustainability through games, little attempts have been made to know the relationship between environmental perceptions and in-game behavior. For instance, Vuong, Ho, Nguyen, et al. (2021) conducted a comprehensive survey of *Nintendo's Animal Crossing: New Horizons (ACNH)* players that revealed a relationship between in-game behaviors and environmental perceptions. A similar study that examined the extent to which anthropocentric attitudes of people reflected in their in-game behaviors showed that players who believed in human dominion were more inclined to engage in negative acts on trees while those who refrained from cutting down trees were more likely to disagree that humans were born to rule others (Ho et al., 2022). This agrees with Janakiraman's (2020) assertion that anthropocentric activities over the period have been the main cause of environmental degradation. To promote environmental sustainability, anthropocentrism environmental values (anti-anthropocentrism) have been shown to promote pro-environmental behaviors (Kaida & Kaida, 2016).

In related works, Johannes et al. (2021) provided a dataset about an investigation on game player behavior and perceptions but the focus of the study was on well-being and motivational dimensions. Vuong et al. (2021) also provided a dataset about the relationship between environmental perceptions and in-game behavior without conducting further analysis to look at the subdomains of environmental perception influence on in-game behavior. The study by Svensson (2016) is one of the few studies that confirm that people's perceptions of environmental elements have implications on their behavior in gaming environments.

1.2. Research gap and study objectives

From the aforementioned studies, it can be deduced that prior works on environmental perceptions and in-game behavior have focused more on how video games or gaming habits influence human behavior or can promote pro-environmental values in individuals (Janakiraman et al., 2018, 2021; UNESCO, 2018). That is, there is less focus on how environmental perception influences in-game behaviors. A few of the studies that looked at how environmental perceptions influence in-game behavioral decisions (Ho et al., 2022; Vuong, Ho, Nguyen, et al., 2021) did not thoroughly provide the categories or dimensions of environmental perceptions that affect in-game behaviors. For example, the study of Ho et al. (2022) focused only on anthropocentric attitudes in a game environment.

Therefore, to overcome this gap, this present study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of how users' environmental perception might impact their gaming behaviors based on the revised New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) scale by Dunlap et al. (2000). NEP is chosen because it measures the five different worldviews about the environmental paradigm, namely: the reality of limits to growth, anti-anthropocentrism, the fragility of nature's balance, rejection of exemptionalism, and the possibility of an eco-crisis. No study, to the best of our knowledge, has considered similar investigation. Therefore, this present study could be considered as the first one that attempts to provide a holistic outlook on how different elements of environmental perceptions of gamers affect their in-game behaviors.

By attempting to ascertain the elements of environmental perceptions and how they impact behavioral decisions in a game environment (depicted in the hypothesis below), the game industry will be able to design games that measure the pro-environmental behaviors of players which can serve as evidence for planning environmental sustainability education. The open data used for the investigation in this present study was sourced and adapted from Vuong et al. (2021). Previous studies have utilized openly accessible datasets to examine players' in-game behavior within gaming environments, laying the groundwork for future research on the relationship between player perceptions and behavior in video games (Aung et al., 2018; Belaza et al., 2020; Drachen et al., 2012). For instance, to understand behavioral patterns of players during gameplay, Drachen et al. (2012) made use of large datasets from the Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Game (MMOG) *Tera* and the multi-player strategy war game *Battlefield 2: Bad Company 2*. Belaza et al. (2020) analyzed the relationship between players' real-world context and their in-game behavior using datasets from *EVE Online*, a large-scale

multiplayer online game that simulates a fantasy galaxy. Aung et al. (2018) also randomly drew the data of 413,341 players from the global player base of *Riot Games*, the developer and publisher of *League of Legends* to study cognitive performance in a gameplay context. In elucidating the significance of their datasets concerning player characteristics, in-game behavior, and performance during gameplay, Liu and Liu (2020) asserted that such data serves as a valuable asset and a pertinent point of reference for researchers delving into the study of diverse player in-game behaviors. This justifies our use of open data sets to investigate how players' environmental perceptions might impact their in-game behaviors towards the environment while playing. We attempt to provide a springboard for further investigations about the interrelations between player perceptions, in-game behavior, and gaming elements.

2. Theoretical background and research hypotheses

The existence of ecological limits to growth is a major theme in environmental literature (Dunlap, 2008) that conveys the notion that there is a self-imposed limitation or a natural-imposed limitation to growth that our industrialized society cannot expand (Meadows et al., 1972). According to Meadows et al. (1972), due to the widespread malnutrition, deteriorating environment, rapid population, and resource depletion, the world may reach a limit which it cannot expand again. We hypothesize that the idea of limits of growth has the capacity to affect in-game behavior. A clear example can be seen in a dictator game where the notion of scarcity of food led to the selfish behavior of gameplayers who were experiencing hunger (Roux et al., 2015). A similar study that involved a child-friendly dictator game also affirmed that hungrier children were less likely to share fewer resources with their peers (Huppert et al., 2020). That is, the sharing decisions of participants were impacted by their hungry state. The study by Ho et al. (2019) showed that in a casino game, the physical environment which is made up of aesthetics and functional attributes in terms of ambience and comfort has an effect on the unplanned gaming behavior of casino customers. In essence, casino's customer's perception of the degree of comfortability and adequacy of design also affects their perception of their own resources which in turn influences their unplanned gaming behaviors. Kassab et al. (2021) also conducted an experiment to illustrate that relative deprivation (the state of feeling unfairly disadvantaged in comparison to others such as living costs, adverse economic conditions, or giving a false feedback, etc.) increases aggressive behavior in a game context. Additionally, in a trust game, cognitive load (e.g., the rapid consumption of media information) was observed to cause participants to express less trust than in the case of no cognitive load and limited

cognitive resources led to a more impulsive behavior than when resources were available. Based on the above literature, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H1. Limits of growth affects players' in-game behaviors.

Anthropocentrism is a worldview that places humans at the center of environmental ethical views, claiming that humans alone possess an intrinsic value and judge the value of other things based on their usefulness (Ho et al., 2022). Anthropocentric or anti-anthropocentric attitude affects the behavioral response of players in a gaming environment. In the study by Ho and his colleagues observed that different levels of anthropocentric attitude correlate with different in-game environmental behaviors. For example, their study showed that in the game *Animal Crossing: New Horizons*, the higher the frequency of a game player going fishing, the higher the chances that the player favors the idea of human dominion over non-human entities. In a tabletop role-playing game, an interview session with two groups of players (Warlock and Sorcerer) on whether or not they will harm crocodiles fleeing from battle showed that the Sorcerer held an anthropocentric worldview and hence was more prone to kill the crocodiles (van Oostveen, 2020). Vuong, Ho, La, et al. (2021) also demonstrated that holding an anti-anthropocentric belief correlates with the frequency of in-game behavior that encourages pro-environmental behaviors. They revealed that a gameplayer that takes wood from a tree has a greater tendency to disagree that humans are meant to rule over nature while players who cut down trees even after taking wood are more likely to possess an anthropocentric worldview. In an attempt to call for game designers to rethink anthropocentrism, Stone (2019) makes an argument that although humans including their anthropocentric attitudes influence gameplay and exert control over it, the game elements can also influence humans with unexpected outcomes. A similar study that proposes a transition from anthropocentrism to a more ecological worldview mentioned that in video games (such as “*Elden Ring*”) the choices of a player affect how the game will end (As, 2022). According to As (2022), the actions of players during gameplay are determined by their moral values which are shaped by their cultural history and upbringing. Based on the above literature, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H2. Anti-anthropocentrism affects players' in-game behaviors.

Using a game-based theory approach, Seaberg et al. (2017) demonstrated in their systematic review that a disruption in the natural balance, such as a natural disaster can affect behavioral responses of actors involved in the disaster. They revealed that individuals tend to be more risk averse during natural disasters. Ma et al. (2013) studied turbulent crowd movement in a

congested environment and observed that although no pedestrian is believed to have pushed the other from the start, body contact among pedestrians induced a force spread which lead to a turbulent flow. The study by Bovan et al. (2018) also showed that a disruption in nature such as a flood affected voting behavior in Croatia. Vardy and Atkinson (2019) also demonstrated that people differentially adjust their prosocial behavior during a disruptive event in nature. That is, a disruption in nature or natural balance can dictate in-person behavior. In the study by Vuong, Ho, Nguyen, et al. (2021), they mentioned that due to the fragility of nature's balance or the reality of life, farmers who love nature may exploit nature to make ends meet. Applying it to a gaming context in the discussion of environmental sustainability, it is proposed that the perception of disruption in nature's balance can also affect the in-game behavior of players. Moreover, Vuong, Ho, La, et al. (2021) established a relationship between game players' environmental perceptions such as fragility of nature's balance and their in-game behavior. Based on the above literature, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H3. The fragility of nature's balance affects players' in-game behaviors.

The concept of human exceptionalism simply refers to the notion that humans are exempt from the constraints of nature, unlike other organisms (Dunlap et al., 2000). For example, Situmorang et al. (2023) declared that people who mostly value exceptionalism ideas although may believe in the threats of climate change have negative perceptions of it (e.g., climate change is exaggerated by the media due to political agenda). According to Situmorang et al. (2023), exceptionalism idea makes people skeptical about the constraints of nature such as climate change and this affects their behavior. Similarly, the behavior of gamers with anti-exceptionalism beliefs is influenced by their perceptions of the environment during gameplay. In the real world, Mensah and Ampofo (2020) performed an analysis to show the predictive power of anti-exceptionalism on human behavior relating to waste management practices. Jeong et al. (2021) also found a positive significant relationship between anti-exceptionalism and environment conservation. The studies by Kim et al. (2021) and Situmorang and Tarigan (2018) all showed that the caring practices, behavioral characteristics, and actions of individuals are influenced by anti-exceptionalism. That is, gamers who hold anti-exceptionalism beliefs have a higher tender to engage in pro-environmental behaviors during gaming. Based on the above literature, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H4. Anti-exceptionalism affects players' in-game behaviors.

Ecocrisis is an environmental, social, and moral problem that results from egoistic behavior and can cause damage to the planet (Kosulya, 2011). Ecocrisis can build survival instincts in individuals or game players. For example, Abraham (2018) mentioned that in the survival-crafting game *Subnautica*, a player's space crash lands on water and has to adopt the survival strategy of using the player's pod to refine simple scraps and other resources into usable raw materials such as knives to catch fish, cook, and eat. According to Abraham, the need to eat and the duration for catching fish to cook and eat to fill a hunger meter can interrupt and incentivize certain decisions during the gameplay. Vuong, Ho, La, et al. (2021) adds that environmental perception such as ecocrisis plays an influential role in behavioral decisions of players during gameplay. Furthermore, Fjællingsdal and Klöckner (2019) mentioned that environmental consciousness (i.e., the extent to which people perceive threats toward the environment as urgent and problematic to everyday lives) combined with feelings of personal responsibility determines ecological behavior. With that being said, it is postulated that perceptions of the possibility of ecocrisis elicit behavioral responses in gaming environments. Based on the above literature, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H5. The Possibility of an eco-crisis affects players' in-game behaviors.

2. Study context

To investigate how students' environmental perception might impact their in-game behaviors, this study uses Nintendo's *Animal Crossing: New Horizons (ACNH)* as the study context. ACNH was launched in 2020 by the Nintendo Switch console. It is an adventure, puzzle and life simulation genre (Hsieh et al., 2021). After choosing their avatars, the players find themselves living on a deserted island with anthropomorphic animal residents. Without any form of competition, they try to complete various in-game activities, such as interacting with computer-controlled animal residents, fishing, planting trees, collecting bugs, wood, and minerals, as well as building and designing houses (Webster, 2020). The players can also be crafted into items, such as useful tools, clothing, and furniture.

ACNH is relevant to the present study context because players can conduct various environmental activities within the game which can harm or protect and develop the ecosystem. Specifically, this present study classifies the players' in-game behaviors to five constructs, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Behavior constructs and the associated in-game activities

Behavior construct	Definition	In-game activities
Contribute to nature (CTN)	The players are doing activities to support and protect the nature	Planting trees Planting flowers Crossbreed flowers Release fish back to nature Release bugs back to nature
Contribute to Science (CTS)	The players are doing activities that contribute to promoting science knowledge and activities	Donate to museums Discover new species Terraforming
Harm nature (HN)	The players are doing activities that harm the nature	Cut-down trees Take woods Sell trees for profit Sell flowers for profit
Harm animals (HA)	The players are doing activities that are harming animals or risk the extinction of animals	Sell fish for profit Sell bugs for profit Send fish as a gift Send bugs as a gift
Discovery (Dis)	The players are doing discovery activities	Find villagers Find resources Enjoy scenery

Therefore, this present study investigates how the players' environmental perception related to the five constructs (see Section 2) might impact their in-game behaviors, specifically, the five in-game behavior constructs in Table 1. Figure 1 presents the research model to be investigated in this study. It should be noted that each of the hypothesis was later on (see Results section) divided to five sub-hypotheses. For instance, during the investigation of H1, the five generated sub-hypotheses are: H1.1: limits of growth might affect players' in-game behaviors related to contributing to nature; H1.2: limits of growth might affect players' in-game behaviors related to contributing to science; and, H1.3: limits of growth might affect players' in-game behaviors related to harming nature; H1.4: limits of growth might affect players' in-game behaviors related to harming animals; and, H1.5: limits of growth might affect players' in-game behaviors related to discovery. For the sake of figure clarity, the sub-hypotheses were not drawn in the research model depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research model related to players' environmental perception and their in-game behaviors

3. Method

This study relies on the open data of Vuong et al. (2021) to investigate the five hypotheses (see Section 2) within the five in-game behavior constructs (see Section 3). It should be noted that this data was restructured and regrouped (based on Table 1) to meet the objective of this present study, as well as to validate the proposed research model depicted in Figure 1.

4.1. Participants

After posting the needed questionnaires, by Vuong et al. (2021), within various ACNH communities on different platforms like Discord, Reddit, and Facebook, 640 participants answered the needed questionnaires. Particularly, 412 participants were females and 228 were males. The participants were from various regions like the US/Canada (55%), Asia (28.13%), and the European Union (EU) (14.38%), while the remaining 2.5% were from other regions. All participants reported that they played ACNH.

4.2. Instruments

Among the several instruments used by Vuong et al. (2021), two were relevant to this present study, as follows:

Participants' perceptions toward environment were measured using the revised New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) scale. NEP was revised and validated by Dunlap et al. (2000). It has been widely applied across disciplines and populations to gauge the pro-environmental orientation (Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010). NEP is a 5 point-Likert scale questionnaire ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). It contains 15 items distributed over the five constructs (limits of growth, anti-anthropocentrism, the fragility of nature's balance, anti-exceptionalism and the possibility of an ecocrisis).

Players' in-game activities (see Table 1) were measured using the in-game behavior questionnaire proposed by Vuong et al. (2021). It is a 5-point Likert which aims to measure the willingness of conducting each of the in-game activities (see Table 1). It ranges from 1 (very unlikely) to 5 (very likely). It contains 18 items distributed over the 5 constructs (see Table 1). An example of the statements is: *How often do you do the following activities with trees? [Plant new trees]*

4.3. Data analysis

SPSS and AMOS software were used for data processing and hypothesis testing of the full structural model. Preliminary research widely used these applications to analyze behavioral data (Khalid et al., 2022; Smeda et al., 2018). In the first stage, the analysis of validity and reliability of the measurement scale was conducted using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The second step uses SPSS to determine descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. Multivariate normality checking using AMOS software was also used to determine the skewness and kurtosis of each variable. The last step is to testing hypotheses between variables, SEM is run using AMOS with maximum likelihood as the method for estimating the parameters.

5. Results

This section starts by validating the constructed research model (see Figure 1), and then by testing the proposed five hypotheses.

5.1. Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics for environmental perceptions and in-game behaviors variables were calculated, as presented in Table 2. Particularly, skewness and kurtosis were calculated to investigate the normality of the data. Table 2 showed that the obtained values were within the recommended range of $[-2.0]$ and $[9.0]$ as recommended by several studies (Schmider, Ziegler, Danay, Beyer, & Bühner, 2010).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the environmental perceptions and in-game behaviors

Variable	Construct	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Environmental perceptions	Limits of growth	1.00	5.00	3.21	.65	-0.07	0.53
	Anti-anthropocentrism	1.33	5.00	3.62	.81	-0.25	-0.90
	The fragility of nature's balance	1.67	5.00	3.74	.67	-0.01	-0.49
	Anti-exceptionalism	1.33	5.00	3.33	.70	0.26	-0.38
	The possibility of an ecocrisis	1.67	5.00	4.13	.74	-0.57	-0.35
In-game behaviors	Contribute to nature	1.00	4.00	3.01	.50	-0.45	0.13
	Contribute to Science	1.00	4.00	3.28	.58	-0.65	0.21
	Harm nature	1.00	4.00	2.63	.59	0.225	-0.641
	Harm animals	1.00	4.00	2.73	.60	0.165	0.361
	Discovery	1.00	4.00	3.02	.61	-0.485	0.161

5.2. Model validation

To check the properties of the measurement scales (see Table 3), the analysis of validity and reliability of the measurement scale was conducted using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Specifically, reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, where the alpha values were 0.78 and 0.83 for the environmental perception and in-game behaviors, respectively. It can, therefore, be concluded that both variable measurements are reliable, as Cronbach's alpha values were above 0.7 (Yu, 2001).

Table 3. Validity and reliability of the measurement model

Variables	Construct	Loading	Cronbach's α
Environmental perceptions (EP)	Limits of growth	0.80	0.78
	Anti-anthropocentrism	0.71	
	The fragility of nature's balance	0.70	
	Anti-exceptionalism	0.73	
	The possibility of an ecocrisis	0.70	
	Contribute to nature	0.51	0.83

In-game behaviors (IGB)	Contribute to Science	0.30	
	Harm nature	0.71	
	Harm animals	0.57	
	Discovery	0.56	

Table 4 investigates the internal consistency reliability of each construct within the environmental perception (EP) scale, where the Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated. The obtained results revealed that all correlation coefficients are significant, implying the internal consistency of all EP constructs.

Table 4. Internal consistency reliability of environmental perceptions constructs

Construct	Limits of growth	Anti-anthropocentrism	The fragility of nature's balance	Anti-exceptionalism	The possibility of an ecocrisis
Limits of growth		0.10*	0.33**	0.16**	0.22**
Anti-anthropocentrism			0.53**	0.56**	0.57**
The fragility of nature's balance				0.45**	0.58**
Anti-exceptionalism					0.52**
The possibility of an ecocrisis					

* $P < .05$; ** $P < .01$

To investigate the internal consistency reliability of each construct of in-game behavior scale, Pearson correlation coefficients were also calculated. Table 5 indicates that the correlation coefficients are significant, implying the internal consistency of in-game behavior constructs.

Table 5. Internal consistency reliability of in-game behavior constructs

Construct	Contribute to nature	Contribute to Science	Harm nature	Harm animals	Discovery
Contribute to nature		0.297**	0.220**	0.337**	0.317**
Contribute to Science			0.123**	0.162**	0.155**
Harm nature				0.456**	0.338**
Harm animals					0.384**
Discovery					

* $P < .05$; ** $P < .01$

Table 6 shows the indexes of the degree-of-freedom (CMIN/df), goodness-of-fit index (GFI), adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI), comparative fit index (CFI), and Root mean square error

of approximation (RMSEA) which are of 4.405, 0.969, 0.925, 0.947 and 0.073, respectively. The results of this model fit the required criteria (see Table 6), hence it is considered with a strong statistical acceptance.

Table 6. The fit indices for the model

Goodness-Fit Indexes	Result Model	Criteria	Decision
CMIN/df	4.405	≤ 5 (Marsh & Hocevar, 1985)	Fit
Probability	0.001	≤ 0.05	Fit
Goodness-of-fit index (GFI)	0.969	> 0.9 (Hooper et al., 2008)	Fit
Incremental fit index (IFI)	0.933	> 0.9 (Bollen, 1990)	Fit
Adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI)	0.925	> 0.9 (Hooper et al., 2008)	Fit
Comparative fit index (CFI)	0.947	> 0.9 (Hu, & Bentler, 1998)	Fit
Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	0.073	< 0.08 (Goretzko et al., 2023)	Fit

5.3.Hypotheses testing

Table 7 presents the results of hypotheses testing. The relationships tested were for the environmental perceptions constructs effect on in-game behaviors constructs. Limits of growth was not related to any of the in-game behavior constructs. Anti-anthropocentrism was positively related to Contribute to Science and negatively related to Harm nature. Fragility of nature's balance was positively related to Contribute to Science, Harm nature, Harm Animals and Discovery. Anti-exceptionalism was negatively related to Harm nature, Harm animals and Discovery. Possibility of an eco-crisis was positively related to Contribute to Science and Discovery, while it was negatively related to Harm animals.

Table 7. Relationships between environmental perceptions and in-game behaviors

Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	P value	Support	
H1	H1.1: Limits of growth → Contribute to nature	.030	.330	No
	H1.2: Limits of growth → Contribute to Science	.040	.251	No
	H1.3: Limits of growth → Harm nature	.044	.216	No
	H1.4: Limits of growth → Harm animals	.050	.174	No
	H1.5: Limits of growth → Discovery	.018	.622	No
H2	H2.1: Anti anthropocentrism → Contribute to nature	.021	.385	No
	H2.2: Anti anthropocentrism → Contribute to Science	.069	.033*	Yes
	H2.3: Anti anthropocentrism → Harm nature	-.103	.001**	Yes
	H2.4: Anti anthropocentrism → Harm animals	-.069	.069	No
	H2.5: Anti anthropocentrism → Discovery	.012	.755	No
H3	H3.1: Fragility → Contribute to nature	.010	.750	No
	H3.2: Fragility → Contribute to Science	.132	.001**	Yes
	H3.3: Fragility → Harm nature	.107	.006**	Yes
	H3.4: Fragility → Harm animals	.140	.001**	Yes
	H3.5: Fragility → Discovery	.128	.001**	Yes
H4	H4.1: Anti-exceptionalism → Contribute to nature	-.013	.652	No

	H4.2: Anti-exceptionalism → Contribute to Science	.009	.826	No
	H4.3: Anti-exceptionalism → Harm nature	-.138	.001**	Yes
	H4.4: Anti-exceptionalism → Harm animals	-.114	.003**	Yes
	H4.5: Anti-exceptionalism → Discovery	-.119	.001**	Yes
H5	H5.1: Possibility → Contribute to nature	.043	.110	No
	H5.2: Possibility → Contribute to Science	.101	.011*	Yes
	H5.3: Possibility → Harm nature	-.001	.980	No
	H5.4: Possibility → Harm animals	-.087	.016*	Yes
	H5.5: Possibility → Discovery	.120	.003**	Yes

* $P < .05$; ** $P < .01$

Figure 2 presents the statistical model of the environmental perceptions, in-game behaviors and their constructs. In addition, Figure 2 presents the standardized estimates of each pair of variables.

Figure 2. The statistical model of the environmental perceptions and in-game behaviors

6. Discussion

This study investigated the effect of players' environmental perceptions on their in-game behaviors while playing the game ACNH. Specifically, a research model of five main hypotheses (with five sub-hypotheses for each hypothesis) was proposed and validated (see Table 7). The obtained results for each of the hypotheses are discussed in the following subsequent sections.

6.1.Limits of growth affects players' in-game behaviors

The findings related to hypothesis 1(H1) that players with limits of growth perception neither contribute to nature (H1.1), nor science (H1.2), nor discovery (H1.5) is in line with the definition that limits of growth do not promote sustainable environmental behavior. However, it was anticipated that the perception of limits of growth will lead to negative environmental behaviors. But as can be seen in hypothesis 1 (H1), although gameplayers did not engage in pro-environmental behaviors, they did not harm nature (H1.3) or animals (H1.4) during gaming. A possible explanation for this is that in resource-rich gaming environments, players will not harm nature or animals. That is, while the idea of resource scarcity can lead to selfish behaviors and competitive orientation (Roux et al., 2015), when there are abundant resources and no or less competition, there is a higher tendency for individuals with the notion of self-imposed limitation or a natural-imposed to growth to remain neutral (neither contributes to nature or harm nature) (Schaerer et al., 2018). Inferring from the statement that the degree of comfortability and adequacy of design affects gameplayers' perception of their own resources which influences their unplanned in-game behavior (Ho et al., 2019).

In a positive light, it can be said that the nature of the game design and the degree of comfortability in accessing resources influenced the behavioral decisions of players in the ACNH. This means that those game designers who include abundant resources or provide a degree of comfortability as parts of the game elements will reduce negative environmental behaviors. In real life, as part of the efforts to promote Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), enough resources should be made available to the population to curb the rate of human destruction of the natural environment.

6.2.Anti-anthropocentrism affects players' in-game behaviors

It is seen that hypothesis 2 (H2) had two significant yet contradictory results, where anti-anthropocentrism people are willing to contribute to science (H2.2), but at the same time are also willing to harm the nature (H2.3). While H2.2 is in line with the definition of anti-anthropocentrism which is the worldview opposing the notion that humankind is the central or

most important element of existence, H2.3 is not. In this context, Vuong, Ho, La et al. (2021) also reported that people who possess an anti-anthropocentric worldview do not always have good behaviors. Specifically, they found that a gameplayer that takes wood from a tree has a greater tendency to disagree that humans are meant to rule over nature. This might be explained by the fact that although humans including their anthropocentric attitudes influence gameplay and exert control over it, the game elements can also influence the players and affect how the game will end (As, 2022; Stone, 2019). For instance, the players in *Animal Crossing: New Horizons*, which is the context of this present study, had to cut some woods (i.e., harm the nature) to, for instance, craft several items that can help them progress in the game (building, discovering, etc.). This was further reflected in our findings related to harm animals (H2.4.), as players were not ready to harm the living creatures in the nature just for their own benefits.

Therefore, to develop players' positive behaviors, hence contributing to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), game designers and developers should promote in-game positive environmental behaviors (not those that might harm the nature), such as plating trees/flowers, land watering, etc., so that the players can have more earnings (e.g., coins, food, etc.), hence further progressing in the game.

6.3. The fragility of nature's balance affects players' in-game behaviors

Following the analysis of perceptions of fragility in nature on in-game behaviors (H3), it was revealed that possessing a view that nature can be disrupted by an external force, such as a natural disaster did not contribute to nature (H3.1), but science (H3.2). The divergent findings can be explained by the fact that people adjust their behaviors differently in a disruptive event in nature (Vardy & Atkinson, 2019). At the same time, individuals might explore scientific perspectives to find solutions to a disruption in nature. Emihovich et al. (2020) mentioned that well-designed games promote problem-solving skills by demanding players to generate new knowledge from challenging scenarios in an interactive environment while at the same time allowing them to hone their problem-solving skills over time in immersive gameplay. Therefore, it can be said that the design features and the immersive nature of ACNH have the ability to promote the problem-solving skills of the game players. As expected, it was shown that perceptions of fragility in nature harm nature (H3.3), animals (H3.4), and discovery (H3.5). As mentioned before, perceptions of fragility in nature might propel individuals to explore nature to make ends meet. It can be deduced that players in the ACNH harmed nature and animals to be able to survive in the game over time. Regarding the harm to discovery, Seaberg et al. (2017)

demonstrated that individuals tend to be more risk-averse when they perceive a disruption or fragility in nature. Thus, game players explored less because they were unwilling to take risks.

6.4. Anti-exceptionalism affects players' in-game behaviors

While perceptions of anti-exceptionalism promote pro-environmental behavior such as good waste management practices (Mensah & Ampofo, 2020), environmental conservation (Jeong et al., 2021), and caring actions (Situmorang & Tarigan, 2018), we found contradictory results in our study. It can be seen that anti-exceptionalism does not contribute to nature (H4.1) or science (H4.2). However, it harms nature (H4.3), animals (H4.4), and discovery (H4.5). The findings can be attributed to cognitive dissonance (when there is a contradiction between principles and actual behavior) (Odou et al., 2019). For example, Young et al. (2010) revealed that about 30% of people believed the environment needs to be protected but only 5% acted on their concerns. Young et al. (2010) mentioned that by fostering attitudinal change and reducing the importance of inconsistent views, cognitive dissonance can be reduced to promote pro-social behaviors. Another explanation for the current findings might be that game elements can also affect the in-game behavior of players. For example, in the study by Leitão et al. (2022) about environmental education, different game elements had different degrees of effects on the recycling behavior of learners. This means that game manufacturer should know which game elements to include in games to encourage good environmental behaviors among players. As declared by Morford et al. (2014), behavior analytic research and practice stand to gain from including successful elements of game design in an effort to address enduring problems of society today pertaining to health and environmental conservation.

6.5. The Possibility of an eco-crisis affects players' in-game behaviors.

The fifth hypothesis revealed that perceptions of the possibility of ecocrisis do not contribute to nature (H5.1) or harm nature (H5.3), but it contributes to science (H5.2) and promotes discovery (H5.5). Nonetheless, it harms animals (H5.4). The current study's findings are in consensus with existing literature in the sense that while the perception of an existential threat can cause game players to build survival instincts to thrive in a game such as harming animals (Abraham, 2018), they might perceive threats to the environment to be problematic and engage in ecological behaviors, such as not harming nature or remaining neutral to avoid further disturbance to the environment (Fjællingsdal & Klöckner, 2019). With that being said, game designers should consider factors that foster better ecological behaviors in gaming environments, such as contributing to nature and science rather than players being neutral. Also,

good environmental education can promote pro-environmental decisions within individuals. Since the game was developed mainly for entertainment without environmental safety or sustainability in mind, researchers and game designers should investigate the veracity of the current study's findings and think of introducing environmental sustainability elements in the game.

7. Conclusions, implications and limitations

This study investigated how players' environmental perceptions might impact their in-game behaviors. Particularly, it offered a comprehensive perspective on how variations in environmental perceptions determine different behavioral decisions in gaming environments. The obtained results revealed that players' environmental perceptions might influence their in-game behaviors, however this is not always the case; the obtained results also revealed that players might behave within the game against their beliefs and perception just to progress within the game. As a result, it can be deduced that the way of designing a given game (i.e., the designed game missions to be completed to move forward in the game or the designed types of game interaction) might also impact the players' behaviors toward the environment, regardless of their environmental perceptions.

The findings of this study can contribute to the literature from different perspectives. From a theoretical perspective, this study contributes to the ongoing debate about how environmental perception might impact players' behaviors in games. This can help in framing various game theories considering different individual differences, including environmental perception. From a practical perspective, the findings of this study were discussed in light of the SDGs, particularly, relating to environmental sustainability in an attempt to inform game designers and developers on how to design games that can promote good ecological behaviors, as well as environmental education instructors on how to gamify learning to encourage good environmental practices.

It should be noted that this study has several limitations that should be acknowledged and further researched. For instance, this study did not investigate how the players' gender or geographical regions might impact their environmental perceptions as well as their in-game behaviors. Therefore, future research could extend the present study by considering these variables as well as other important individual differences within players (e.g., personality, player type). Additionally, this study relied only on the self-report method to measure players' in-game behaviors. While this method is effective, it may not always be accurate (Tlili et al.,

2016). We acknowledge that the self-report method used and the focus on only one game (ACNH) might present limitations on the generalizability of the findings. It is therefore suggested that future research should collect the log data of players during the playing process and analyze them to have more accurate results that can reveal in-depth insights. Our future work will focus on collecting the log data of players during gameplay in various games (beyond the ACNH game) to further conduct a cross-analysis and comparison of these in-gaming behaviors (in different gaming settings), hence developing an in-depth understanding of the relationship between players' environmental perceptions and their in-game behavior. Despite these limitations, this present study is considered one of the early attempts to understand the relationship between players' environmental perception and their in-game behaviors, hence laying as a solid foundation for future research studies who are interested in this line of research.

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